

CAMPHOROSMA LESSINGII LITV. - A VALUABLE FODDER PLANT FOR RECLAMATION OF SALINE AND DROUGHT-PRONE AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPES

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Abstract. *The given article presents new findings on the status of the natural populations of the camphorosma – a valuable fodder range land wild species to be cultivated into a halophytic farming system on agrolandscapes severely affected by drought and salinization in Karakalpakstan.*

Keywords: *halophytes, salinity, fodder species, yield, pasture conservation.*

Introduction: At present time, the most salinity-resistant halophyte species are gradually being introduced into production worldwide as a source of feed and raw materials for livestock, food, and pharmaceutical industries. In the last 15-20 years, large-scale comprehensive studies have been conducted to study the wild flora of halophytes. The natural vegetation of the deserts of Uzbekistan is rich in representatives of wild halophytes, mainly due to genera belonging to the family Amaranthaceae (former Chenopodiaceae). *Camphorosma monspeliaca* L is C4-non succulent euhalophyte, which tolerates cold winters and it is best suited to the sharply continental climate in Central Asian desert and semideserts. On the open pastures it is well grazed by domestic and wild animals due to its highly nutritional forage for small ruminants and camels, well consumed during fall and winter period after leaching of mineral substances. Expected yield in *Artemisia* steppe varies 0.06 to 1.2 t DM/ha. During early stage of vegetation significant amount of mineral salt, volatile oil, microelements and amino acids available.

It is important to suggest that *Camphorosma* species is recommended for improvement and/or creation of long-term, mainly autumn-winter pastures (1). *Camphorosma monspeliaca* L is known to be a source of essential oils and alkaloids and has medicinal value as a stimulant, aphrodisiac, diuretic, and diaphoretic; it is also used to treat lung diseases (2).

However, due to climate change, species of the genus *Camphorosma* are close to being threatened and endangered, as they have been identified as needing attention for conservation status.

The main goal of our article was to study floristic composition, population size and seasonal dynamics of fodder biomass of *Camphorosma monspeliaca* under its natural habitat in different rangelands plant communities. The condition for cultivating *Camphorosma* on salt affected abandoned lands was recommended.

Research materials and methods: The description of vegetation taking into account its floristic composition was carried out using the Drude method generally accepted in geobotany [3]. The traditional route method of geobotanical studies, as well as methods of office interpretation of satellite images Landsat, MODIS, Google. Literary sources were used to clarify the distribution area of plant associations and key species. To study the seasonal dynamics of forage mass in control pasture plots, transects of 10 m² were laid out and mowed, then the biomass of forage plants and their nutritional value were determined using laboratory methods [4]. Pasture types were identified in accordance with the scheme of pasture typology of Uzbekistan (Methodological recommendations for geobotanical survey of natural forage lands of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 1980) [3]. The areas of the contours were determined using GIS methods. Phenology was carried out according to the method of I. N. Beideman [5]. Species affiliation of plants was carried out by the Central Asian plant guides and the Keys to the Central Asian Plants identifier (vol. I-X, 1968-1993), as well as according to the global taxonomic classification. Soil salinity was determined using a portable pH & EC tester - Hanna pH / Conductivity / TDS. The experimental site (ES) "Karabuga" was created by us on abandoned saline lands in the irrigated massif "Karabuga", Karauzyak district in Karakalpakstan. This site is one of the most vulnerable areas in this region due to the lack of irrigation water, soil salinization, significant impact of desertification and salt-dust storms.

It is known to everyone, the soil preparation for sowing/planting halophytes at Karabuga EI met the requirements of a whole range of agrotechnical measures: high-quality plowing with laser planning was carried out. Such preparation improves the water, air and nutrient regime for plants, creates conditions for better accumulation, preservation and economical use of soil moisture, uniform seeding depth, and ensures good growth and development of plants. Before sowing seeds, the soil is additionally loosened with a chisel and irrigation furrows are cut. In this case, the slope of the irrigated area was set at a level of at least 5%. Taking into account the physical and mechanical properties of the soils of the irrigated areas, the slope was increased to 10% or more.

Results and discussion: Vegetation formation in the Aral Sea region proceeds strictly along the paths of the formation of desert-type plant communities of Central Asia, with predominantly halophilic and psammophilic tree-shrub formations of vegetation. [6]. As a result of reconnaissance field work and geobotanical surveys of halophytic vegetation of the salt desert of the Aral Sea basin, about 126 plant species were included in the electronic database of halophytes with a focus on rare, endangered and economically significant species of the desert flora of the Aral Sea basin. Many of those described by us should be included in the Global Biodiversity Information System (GBIF).

Assessment of pasture lands of Karakalpakstan. Pasture territories of Karakalpakstan occupy vast areas, and they are a reserve for further development of desert-pasture livestock farming. However, due to significant salinization of the soil, halophytes dominate in the vegetation cover, characterized by relatively low nutritional and forage productivity, narrow seasonality of plant palatability (mainly autumn-winter season). Forage plants grow in the territories of Karakalpakstan with different soil and climate characteristics and have different nutritional and energy value in feeding animals, related to their vegetation phase and the possibility of preparing backup stocks of feed, their processing for feeding animals. Ensuring uninterrupted access to quality feed is one of the key issues in the development of livestock in Karakalpakstan. The small

size of rural household plots limits the supply of feed to livestock bred by farmers. As a rule, households purchase additional feed for winter-spring feeding of livestock in local markets and neighboring areas. Grazing of livestock along roadsides and irrigation canals is widespread.

Definitely, such land use methods damage soil fertility and the ecosystem as a whole. At the same time, alternative agricultural methods, in the context of climate change, on the one hand, should generate income for the rural population and be more profitable, and on the other hand, be environmentally friendly (ecologically-friendly) and serve the restoration of natural ecosystems - for their sustainable use and conservation.

Taking into consideration the natural pastures of the project area, in the Karauzyak district, natural pastures are the main source of feed for small cattle. Due to the expansion of areas under grain crops, there is a decrease in irrigated areas under forage crops, which has led to an acute shortage of feed, both in pasture areas and on agricultural lands. The main natural vegetation of the pastures consists of poorly palatable species, such as *Zygophyllum oxianum*, *Suaeda salsa*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Phragmites australis*, *Caragana halodendron*, *Aeluropus litoralis*, *Tamarix hispida*, *Halostachys caspica*, and *Karelina caspia*.

Besides that, the vegetation cover of the used pastures is diverse, with the dominance of halophyte plants (Halophyta) and *Phragmites* reed, which is very well eaten by cattle at the beginning of the growing season. The average yield of such pastures is 2.8-7.0 c/ha of edible mass. The local population mows young shoots of reeds and uses them for animal feed. With intensive mowing of reed shoots, the afterglow is restored very quickly, otherwise the old plants become coarse and turn into poorly edible animal feed. In the project area, we documented the main foci of distribution of 78 wild species for further introduction into the system (closed cycle) of arid halophytic agriculture. The best results in terms of accumulation of green biomass and formation of high-quality seeds were shown by halophytic species such as *Bassia scoparia*, *Atriplex nitens*, *Climacoptera aralensis*, *C. lanata*, *Suaeda salsa*, *Suaeda altissima*, *Caroxylon sclerantha*, *Caroxylon dendroides*, *Salicornia persica*, *Agropyron fragile*, *Alhagi pseudalhagi*), which are recommended to be grown both in pure crops and in various combinations with non-traditional underutilized crops such as *Sorghum bicolor*, *Penisetum glaucum*, *Setaria italica*, *Chenopodium quinoa*, *Charthamnus tinctorius*, *Helianthus tuberosus*, *Vigna radiata*, *Sesame indicum*, *Glycine max* and *Amaranthus retroflexus* var. *virescens* [7,8]. Within the framework of the project, encouraging results were obtained on the experimental site "Karabuga" on the species diversity and formation of agrobiocenoses of desert vegetation through the introduction of fodder halophytes in combined crops of non-traditional crops. Among the halophytic species, *Camphorosma lessingi* - *Camphorosma monspeliaca* L. subspecies *C lessingi* occupies an important place as a fodder crop (the consumption of camphorosma hay by cattle reaches 80%). In natural habitats, this semi-shrub, 25-80 cm high, with short woody branches that form a turf on the soil with bunches of leaves and with ascending whitish annual shoots; the taproot system penetrates to a depth of 2-8 m: the projective cover of the earth's surface with plants reaches 85-90%.

Moreover, *camphorosma* begins to vegetate in April, blooms in July, August, the fruits ripen in late October - early November. The duration of the vegetation period is 235 days. The yield of dry forage biomass in the fruit ripening phase reaches 0.5-1.2 t / ha, seeds - 0.03 t / ha. 100 kg of hay contains 3.4 kg of digestible protein, 26.8 feed units. As a salt-tolerant, frost-resistant and grazing-resistant plant, it is widely used to improve natural and create cultural long-vegetating

autumn-winter pastures, can be used to improve solonetz and saline pastures. At the beginning of the growing season, a large number of mineral salts, essential oils, microelements and amino acids accumulate in plants, which allows the use of this plant in medical practice.

Due to the sparse cover of camphorosma in the conditions of the Aral Sea region, in November 2023 we studied the thickets (populations) of camphorosma in its natural habitat on the salt marshes of Farish district of Jizzakh region of Uzbekistan (Issyk-Kul tract). Camphorosma plant associations are concentrated on a gently sloping, slightly hummocky slope - the base of a small elevation (10-12 m) near Lake Issyk-Kul (photo 1).

Photo 1. The area of growth of casphorosma in Farish district of Jizzakh region

The habitat of casphorosma in Farish district of Jizzakh region

What is more interesting, the soil cover is represented by solonchak desert-sand accumulations and silt-lake deposits. The soil surface is covered with semi-decomposed remains of camphorosma vegetation in the form of a salty dust-sand mixture. Visually, medium-strong salinization is detected on the soil surface, which can be traced throughout the entire soil profile, gradually decreasing to a depth of 1 m. The hydrogen index (pH) and specific electrical conductivity of water (EC, mS / cm) near the located Issyk-Kul Lake were 12.02 pH and 5.43 mS / cm, respectively, which indicates high salinity of water and soil. In this area, camphorosma grows as a landscape plant and prevails over other species of the community in terms of mass 45.6 ± 0.78 and cover 89.6 ± 1.33 . The population size is relatively constant.

The most constant indicators are the average statistical population size 33.0 ± 0.44 , as well as mass. Data on the variation coefficient C_v indicate a slight variability of indicators 3.32-5.33%, which indicates the evenness of individuals in the natural population. The average varying indicator was the number of shoots C_v equal to 15.1% (Table 1).

Additionally, the yield of forage mass of camphorosma in natural conditions, in the fruit ripening phase, reaches 12.0-15.1 c/ha. At the end of the growing season, in November, animals eat up to 70-85% of the plants. The cenosis includes salt-loving wormwood *Artemisia halophyla* and yantak *Alhagi pseudalhagi*. In 2022 and 2023, seeds of camphorosma (*Camphorosma monospeliaca* of *lessingii* subs.) and salt-loving wormwood (*Artemisia halophyla*) were collected

and seedlings were prepared in Issyk-Kul tract in order to form artificial agrobiocenoses of desert vegetation and conduct tests within the framework of the SATREPS project at the Panayev Farm experimental site.

Table 1. Abundance indicators of camphorosma *Camphorosma monspeliaca of lessingi* subspecies in the natural population (Issyk-Kul tract)

№	Indicator	M ±m	G	Cv	t
1	Plant weight, g	45,6±0,78	1,83	4,01	60,0
2	Projective cover, %	89,6±1,33	2,98	3,32	67,4
3	Projective cover	33,0±0,44	1,76	5,33	75,0
4	Number of shoots, pcs	10,4±0,70	1,57	15,1	14,9

Note: M is the arithmetic mean, m is the error of the mean, G is the standard deviation, Cv is the variation coefficient, t is the indicator of the study accuracy.

Table 2. Coordinates of the collection site of seeds and seedlings of forage plants 23.11. 2023

№	Plants names	N	E	Alt,m
1	Camphorosma lessingii	40 ⁰ 39'40,1	067 ⁰ 06'26,4	274
2	Artemisia halophyla	40 ⁰ 39'34,5	067 ⁰ 03'59,1	279

Scientific experiments on the Karabuga experimental plot. The objective of scientific research at the initial stage on Karabuga experimental plot was to study various types of local halophytes, including camphorosma, under saline conditions with the aim of widely introducing them into forage production practice. In 2022, camphorosma was planted in the experimental field with seedlings and sown with seeds at the rate of 6 kg per 1 ha. Field germination of seeds was high and amounted to 35%, seedling survival rate - 85%. As the analysis results showed, on the Karabuga plot, strong and very strong salinization prevails along the entire meter profile. Moreover, the salt content increases from spring to autumn. In 2023, halophyte crops were concentrated on a small plot; on the rest of the plot, due to severe soil salinization and poor seed germination, the crops were sparse, with weeds predominating. The optimal time for sowing fodder halophytes is winter-early spring (December-April), which allows for uniform shoots to be obtained due to precipitation. The optimal seeding depth for camphorosma is 1-2 cm. To obtain the desired grass density, the following seeding rates for camphorosma are recommended: 6 kg/ha.

It is important to suggest that plant survival was high - up to 94.4%. The plant height was 32.5±1.54 cm in spring, 48.4±0.37 cm in autumn, the variation coefficient Cv for this trait in spring indicates insignificant variability of the indicators - 8.18%, in autumn 1.32%. Under 2023 conditions, the hay yield of camphorosma was 5.3±0.15 c/ha, the coefficient of variation Cv for this trait also indicates a slight variability of the indicators of 4.90%. The seed yield was 30±0.03 kg/ha, the coefficient of variation Cv was 1.90% (Table 3).

Table 3. Productivity indicators of camphorosma *Camphorosma monspeliaca of lessingi* subspecies at Karabuga State Agricultural University (2023)

Number of plants, thousand pcs/ha*)		Height, cm		Yield, t/ha	
15.V	29. IX	15.V	29.IX	Dry weight	of seeds
36/100	34/94,4	32,5±1,54	48,4±0,37	0.53±0,15	0,03±0,003

Note: *) The numerator is the number of plants, the denominator is the survival rate

Conclusion. By summarizing it is important to suggest that based on the results of studies in 2022 and 2023, it was found that, in saline areas, it is advisable to grow camphorosma along

with other halophytic species. Wild halophytes in mixed halophytic farming on saline farmland with limited irrigation form a huge amount of green biomass. The ability to resume growth of halophytes allows them to be used for multiple mowing and haymaking. Multiple mowing allows to get easily eaten forage on the aftermath. The quality of seeds is not affected by toxic salts, which allows these species to be gradually introduced into the livestock feeding system. However, the heavy granulometric composition of clay-loamy soils is less suitable for growing wild halophytes.

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